

Climateurope2

M5: Annual information exchange of WP2 with WP1 for synthesis reports

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A. Summary

A. In Climateurope2, WP2 is central because it deals with standards and guidelines of both data and processes. Those will have impact throughout the whole project, and it will provide those who built climate services important insights. Milestone M5 summarises the major results of the work that took place in WP2 within the first year of the project. This state-of-the-art review is very extensive, and will serve as a basis to recommend standards and guidelines for climate services components.

B. Key Messages

As can be seen in the annex, the number of standards and guidelines is very high, and it is difficult, at a first glance, to make sense of all those standards. The analysis of those standards and guidelines will begin in year 2 of the project. A significant work will be to classify, prioritise, assess, at different levels, and for different types of categories of users and for different objectives. In the table below can be found initial key messages that are prior to the analysis of standards and guidelines.

Key messages	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• The landscape of standards is highly fragmented.• FAIR aspects are leading several actions and are very common, pushed by the RDA and by EC funded projects.• WMO has developed numerous reports/guidelines and requirements linked to climate services and which use specific ISO standards, mainly ISO 9000 on quality management systems.• Climate Services have not been considered in any formal standardisation processes, thus there are not “climate service” focus formal standards• Uncertainties and risks are a very important part in the needed guidelines.• The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) related work has driven many advancements in standardisation and quality control.• Many standards from different communities may be important in the context of climate services because of impact and adaptation studies that need data from other scientific communities than climate science.
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| | <ul style="list-style-type: none">• There is a long list of communities working on and developing standards and guidelines that can impact climate services components. |
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B. Annex

B.1. Summary

This annex lists a series of exchanges of information between WP2 and WP1 throughout the first year of the project, consisting of

- (a) one-on-one meetings between these WPs,
- (b) documents and reference sharing, as well as
- (c) actual text contributions to the synthesis report, which are included in another document following the template provided by WP1.

B.2. Information exchanges

Regular meetings with WP1 were conducted during the first years of Climateurope2 to provide WP2's expertise and point of view on diverse topics, including exchange of information on the list of available guidance documents, recommendations and standards, as well as to discuss accessibility to additional standards, all contributing to the synthesis report directly or in terms of context provision.

The following list includes references as titles and hyperlinks to the documents, teams and institutional websites shared with WP1:

Literature:

- [Assessing the Quality of Regional Climate Information](#)
- [A Geo-Dashboard Concept for the Interactively Linked Visualization of Provenance and Data Quality for Geospatial Datasets](#)
- [FAIR data maturity model](#)
- [FAIR metrics in EOSC](#)

- [Quality information sharing and reusing](#)
- [Ten simple rules for making a vocabulary FAIR](#)
- Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement ([GUM](#))
- For other WPs:
 - [Understanding and managing trust](#)
 - https://pdf.usaid.gov/pdf_docs/PA00KJXW.pdf
 - Capacity building: approaches of the [Irish Marine Institute](#) and [Hewitt et al. 2020](#)
 - [Labelling](#) and IEA perspective on [labelling](#) and [labelling](#) nap perspective and [labelling](#) energy perspective
 - [WTO](#) principles for standards
 - Working Arrangements between [ISO and WMO](#)
 - [Case studies](#) for WP3
 - ISO 17000 conformity assessment (main ISO family for certification/accreditation)
 - [European Accreditation](#)
 - Climate information from [economic perspective](#)
 - [Differentiation of certification standards](#)
 - Process for standard creation in [RESIN](#) project
 - [Narrowing the climate information usability gap](#)
 - [EU standardisation mandates](#)
 - European commission [standards perspective](#), open [questions](#) about standards
 - Surveying Climate Services: [What Can We Learn from a Bird's-Eye View?](#)
 - [Successful climate services](#) for adaptation
 - General structure of a climate service: [C3S case study](#)
- [Concepts](#): standard, guideline, quality management, licence, [certification](#)
- <https://climateinformation.org/>
- These two WMO publications do not seem relevant for us: [country case studies](#), [climate action](#)
- [Standardisation in urban climate adaptation](#): useful to both task 4 and WP1. It lists relevant ISO standards explained, it refers to processes in the urban adaptation strategy, it contains references to risk and vulnerability assessments, it reports criteria for selecting standards (coverage and status) and first steps for certification in climate change adaptation. It also reports lessons learned about difficulties the project had in influencing standards development (Carlo read it)
- Climate change [uncertainties](#): it gives overview of the observations and model types most used in climatology, how bias and uncertainty are computed, strengths and limitations of each climate dataset type, how to downscale, the role of scenarios and their uncertainty
- Deep uncertainty: Walker, Warren E., Robert J. Lempert, and Jan H. Kwakkel, "Deep Uncertainty", in Gass, S. and M. Fu (eds.), *Encyclopedia of Operations Research and Management Science*, Third Edition, Springer, 2013 [DOI 10.1007/978-1-4419-1153-7].
- CMEMS [quality](#): it explains challenges and current situation about quality management at CMEMS, it doesn't go much into details but there a few good practices and focused solutions
- Satellite [quality](#) and [framework](#): it gives overview of the efforts done in Earth satellite community to assess their datasets according to standardised templates, ranking systems, quality indicators and documentary procedures. It is considered a standard for uncertainty estimate in the satellite community, it lacks operational setting of general quality management, it is very much focused on the scientific quality.
- [EO Industry Certification Scheme](#): it provides steps required for getting certified as EO company giving products or service on the market. The steps defined include determination of requirements, documentation needs, development planning and verification, competence of personnel.
- [Metadata management](#) by GEO: it includes requirements for metadata, catalogue, preservation, provenance

- [Data management](#) principles: two pages describing basic principles
- [WMO](#) best practices and [code registry](#)
- [Matching](#) FAIR and CoreTrustSeal
- [FAIR](#) and Earth science data
- [FAIR](#) and data management
- [FAIR](#) automatic validator
- FAIR software [here](#) and [here](#) and [here](#)
- Software quality in [EOSC](#); platform service quality in [EOSC](#): maturity of software based on TRL indicators, ISO 9126, ISO 25010, RRLs (reuse readiness levels) defined by NASA Earth Science Data Systems, DevOps approach (Humble and Farley 2011). The EOSC synergy structured a software quality architecture based on: plan, execution, badge/stamp delivery. The architecture Identified three types of badges: gold, silver, and bronze. The minimum requirements to have the bronze badge is that the software has documentation, licence, code metadata, and is accessible. It was presented also how the platform quality of a software is tested, in addition to simple software the platform requires a support service for communication and reporting with users. EOSC synergy created a self-standing interface (based on yml files) for the users to check the quality of their software, they name this tool SQAaas (Software Quality Assurance as a service). SQAaas releases a quality report and a badge. The assessment is clearly all automated, for things that would require human assessment like clarity and completeness of documentation the assumption is that users will report a ticket through the support service to report lack of documentation.
- Best practices in [oceanography](#)
- Guidelines for climate services from [CLIMATE SENSE](#)
- [Interoperability framework](#) in EOSC (in appendix F analysis of governance frameworks)
- [OGC](#) standards
- [METCE](#) standard
- Open Archival Information System (or [OAIS](#))
- [ETCCDI](#) defines a core set of 27 climate indices, which was subsequently expanded by ET-SCI (cf Appendix A of the [Climpact2 documentation](#))
- IS-ENES in coordination with international partners involved in climate indices production and software extended standards based on CF-Convention to support climate indices: [clix-meta](#)
- Earth observation industry [certification scheme](#): very interesting perspective from industry side about necessary requirements to guarantee satellite datasets meet expected characteristics
- [ASCII File Format Guidelines](#) for Earth science data
- Stewardship [maturity matrix](#): it describes how the maturity matrix at WMO are structured and evaluated
- Metadata [quality assessments](#)
- [Forecast verification](#) methods
- INSPIRE Directive for spatial data <https://inspire.ec.europa.eu/>
- Data exchange standards: WMO [information system](#) (WIS); WMO [Manual on the Global Telecommunication System](#) (GTS) (9); WMO [Manual on Codes](#)
- Engaged in the review of the Climate Data Management Specification 2023 Edition. Particularly focussing on the requirement and definitions around Data Provenance. The opportunity for a joint workshop between WP2 and the WMO Expert team of data requirements is under discussion and likely to happen in 2023.
- [Assessment of the existing resourcing and quality assurance of current climate services](#): deliverable from EU-MACS about business model, market situation for climate services and the role of quality
- Uncertainty and risk:

- [Framing climate uncertainty: socio-economic and climate scenarios in vulnerability and adaptation assessments](#)
- [Understanding the Various Perspectives of Earth Science Observational Data Uncertainty](#)
- [Communicating uncertainty in seasonal and interannual climate forecasts in Europe](#)
- [NUSAP](#)
- [Deep uncertainty](#)
- [Uncertainty for satellite datasets](#) and [here](#) and [here](#)
- [Acute climate risks in the financial system](#)
- Standards:
 - ISOs 14090/1/2/7, 19158/7, 19115, 37122/3 (smart city indicators), 14050, 17025
 - ISO/TC 146 (air quality), ISO/TC 147 (water quality), ISO/TC 113 (hydrometry), ISO/TC 180/SC 1 (solar energy, climate - measurement and data), ISO/TC 211 (geographic information), 3166 (country codes)
 - [INSPIRE directive](#)
 - [Climate and Forecasting \(CF\) Conventions](#) community standard for netCDF metadata
 - [Climate and Forecasting \(CF\) Standard Names](#), which conforms to the [RDA I-ADOPT Framework ontology](#) to facilitate interoperability.
 - Attribute Convention for Data Discovery ([ACDD 1-3](#))
 - C3S [Understanding the Common Data Model – Climate Data Store Toolbox 1.1.5 documentation](#)
 - RDA [Common Information Model](#)
 - Industry: [InetQI](#)
 - [GeoSPARQL](#)
 - [Geonames](#)
 - [FGDC.gov](#)
 - [ATMODAT](#)
 - Checklist for [Climate Services Implementation](#)
 - [OGC](#) standards
 - WMO principles of [information management](#)

Teams/projects/communities:

- WMO Expert Teams
 - [Data Standards](#)
 - [Metadata Standards](#)
 - [Information Management](#)
 - [Climate Services Information System Operations](#)
 - [Data Requirement for Climate Services](#)
 - [Audit and certification](#)
- <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/data-governance-act>
- [Deep uncertainty](#)
- eScience Centre
- GERICS
- National ISO [representative bodies](#)
- SIRMA [project](#)
- International bodies: WMO, OGC, ESA, EUMETSAT, EEA, European Energy Research Alliance (EERA)
- GeoKur Dresden University
- ESMValTool & ISENES project
- FAIRsFAIR, GOFAIR

- RDA [data fitness](#)
- [GEO](#) group of earth observations
- RDA and [ESIP](#); ESIP [quality cluster](#)
- [CMUG CCI](#)
- EUDAT
- [CCS](#) pilot
- ET-DDS (WMO Expert Team on Data Development and Stewardship) or ET-DRC (WMO Expert Team on Data Requirements for Climate) for the WMO Climate Data Portal maturity matrix assessments
- ISO [Climate Action Kit](#)
- [ARDC](#)
- <https://wcdirectory.ametsoc.org/>
- <https://www.ametsoc.org/index.cfm/ams/education-careers/careers/ams-professional-certification-programs/certified-consulting-meteorologist-program-ccm/>